

**TECHNOLOGY - MEDIATED INSTRUCTION'S CHALLENGES: ITS EFFECT
TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY
ENGINEERING MATHEMATICS STUDENTS IN A UNIVERSITY
IN SULU, SOUTHERN PHILIPPINES**

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this research was to find out the challenges in technology mediated-instruction; its effect to academic performance among Grade 11 STEM students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. This study focused on the Challenges encountered on Technology-Mediated Instruction as perceived by the Grade 11 STEM students from STEM 1 to 5 at MSU-Sulu Senior High School. This did not include other issues or benefits of Technology - Mediated Instruction to students out of the target respondents. Additionally, this study was most interest not only to the students, but as well as to their teachers, parents, administration and future researchers. In this study, grades of the students were noted, and checklist questionnaire was used as a research instrument wherein researchers immersed themselves in order to investigate if the academic performance of the students is affected by the challenges in Technology-Mediated Instruction. 2.47% was the total grand mean for the challenges in Technology - Mediated Instruction which falls on the scale disagree. 88.38% for the level of academic performance with a verbal description of very satisfactory. Additionally, for the significant relationship between the challenges in Technology-Mediated Instruction and academic performance.

Keywords: *technology-mediated instruction, challenges, academic performance*

INTRODUCTION

Technology - Mediated Instruction, also known as Blended Learning, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with physical place-based classroom methods. It requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some elements of student control over time, place, patch or pace. While students still attend back-and-mortar schools with a teacher present, face to face classroom practices are combined with computer-mediated activities regarding content and delivery. It is also used in professional development and training setting.

Sabbaha N. et. al, (2024) Learning is the soul of education that eliminates ignorance within individual's mind, it is an ability possessed by human being that plays a crucial role in the existence of human life, from the moment a person was brought into this world, the process of learning begins until he or she reaches the stage of late adulthood which means that learning is a continuous process. Jailani, A. et.al, (2024) Although the pandemic may have passed by now, its effects are still felt, thus education needs to continue. Indeed, education is the key to success, thus it shouldn't be interrupted, so the government has come up with a way to meet the demands of the learners while allowing the children to continue their education, that is why we have idea of the so called Technology-Mediated Instruction.

Balla, F.J. (2024) In today's 21st century, students are facing multiple problems such as explanations based on science and technology and it will likely offer corrective measures of difficulties and definitely one way to traverse these difficulties and challenges is to have Technology-Mediated Instruction.

Bluic, Goodyear and Ellis (2007), In their review of research into Technology Mediated - Instruction, argue that research so far has been focused on different aspects of Technology Mediated - Instruction, especially technology, and they argue for a more holistic approach which seeks to understand the complexity of Technology Mediated - Instruction setting and processes as part of a whole system. For Aldosemani et al. (2018), the lack of internet connection, language barriers, poor financially for Technology Mediated - Instruction initiation are some of the challenges that students are experiencing on the use of Technology Mediated - Instruction. Hence, students should be supported with right financial as this new platform of learning can be costly, added by the fact as such, the use of technology tools are highly needed.

Just as there are many definitions of Technology Mediated - Instruction, there are many reasons why Technology Mediated - Instruction is becoming increasingly popular and beneficial to all the learners. Institutions of higher education are using blended instruction to improve pedagogy, increase access to and the flexibility of learning environments, and improve cost-effectiveness, but the most common reason is to improve pedagogical practices.

The impact of Technology Mediated - Instruction as it offers challenges to students, it might become way for them to become stronger or might result to a total failure. Park & Choi (2009) Research shows that the failure of learners to continue their online education in some

cases has been due to family support or increased workload leading to learner dropout as well as little time for study.

The researchers selected this topic because of their supposition to determine what are the challenges that most students face on their academic journey. As we observe, there is no educated and successful people who were not tested by sort of challenges before they succeeded in life. Additionally, we want to know the strategies employed by the students on the challenges encountered on Technology - Mediated Instruction Modalities.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the Challenges in Technology-Mediated: Its Effect to the Academic Performance among Grade 11 STEM Students in Mindanao State University – Sulu. Hence, this study has sought answers given by the following questions below:

1. What are the Challenges encountered by the Grade 11 STEM students in MSU-Sulu during Technology - Mediated Instruction?
2. What is the level of Academic Performance of Grade 11 STEM students in MSU-Sulu during Technology - Mediated Instruction?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the Challenges in Technology - Mediated Instruction and Academic Performance among grade 11 STEM students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Mindanao State University - Sulu Senior High School Department. The said senior high school is located at Capitol Site, Patikul, Sulu with an approximately distance of 1.3 kilometers from Jolo town. This department was established in 2016. It has two buildings. The first and main building can be found near the campus gymnasium, while the second building which is considered its Administration Building is situated between the College of Arts and Sciences and the old building of the College of Agriculture. Furthermore, it offers the strands General Academic Strand (GAS) and Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM).

Sampling Method

This study utilized the Stratified Random Sampling. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller subgroups known as strata. In stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling has numerous applications and benefits, such as studying population demographics and life expectancy. Stratified random sampling is also called proportional random sampling or quota random sampling.

Research Instrument

The researchers used a checklist questionnaire type wherein the respondents were asked to put a check to show their impression by reading each statement. In this research study, the researchers produced (109) copies of questionnaires as it is the total number of respondents and these were distributed personally after permission was granted.

The questionnaires are divided into two parts: Part I is gathering information on student's demographic profile which includes the name, age, section, and General Average of Performance during the 1st semester of the respondents and Part II is determining the Challenges Encountered on Technology Mediated - Instruction as perceived by the Grade 11 STEM Students.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researchers utilized various statistical treatment of data in order to evaluate and assess the information needed to answer the research questions of the topic. The type of statistical treatment of data utilized were Weighted Mean, Arithmetic Mean, and Chi-square. Weighted Mean was used to know the Challenges encountered in Technology Mediated - Instruction by the grade 11 STEM Students of MSU-Sulu. Arithmetic Mean to identify the level of Academic Performance of the grade 11 STEM Students of MSU-Sulu. Furthermore, Chi-square to determine if there is a significant relationship between the Challenges in Technology Mediated – Instruction and Academic Performance among grade 11 STEM students.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on the challenges encountered by the Grade 11 STEM students in MSU-Sulu during Technology - Mediated Instruction. The participant of this study is delimited to the Grade 11 STEM students in Mindanao State University - Sulu. Furthermore, the study is confined in the second semester of the academic year 2022-2023 and conducted only in Senior High School Building in Mindanao State University-Sulu.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result and discussion of the study, the presentation of data followed the sequence according to the order of the research questions indicated in the statement of the problem or research questions.

Table 4.1. Challenges encountered by the Grade 11 STEM students in MSU-Sulu during Technology Mediated – Instruction.

STATEMENTS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. Slow internet connection	3.16	Agree
2. Constant distraction from social media and household chores	2.72	Agree

3. Too much activities to accomplish	2.70	Agree
4. Poor understanding towards some subjects	2.48	Disagree
5. Poor task management	2.44	Disagree
6. Lack of learning materials	2.39	Disagree
7. Lack of feedback from some teachers	3.37	Disagree
8. It enhanced my capacity during the modular learning.	2.37	Disagree
9. Lack of interest in the subjects	2.06	Disagree
10.No gadget to use for researching	2.01	Disagree
Overall Mean	2.47	Disagree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 (strongly disagree); 1.76 – 2.50 (disagree); 2.51 – 3.25 (agree); 3.36 – 4.00 (strongly agree)

As shown in **table 4.1**, the results revealed for the following statements that were agreed by the respondents: Slow internet connection, Constant distraction from social media and household chores and Too much activities to accomplish, since all mean falls between 2.51 – 3.25.

Whereas the students disagreed on the following statements: Poor understanding towards some subjects, Poor task management, Lack of learning materials, Lack of feedback from some teachers, Poor learning environment, Lack of interest in the subjects, and No gadget to use for researching, since all mean falls between 1.76 – 2.50.

The statements, however, is comprises of ten (10) numbers, wherein seven (7) of them signify as disagree, while the remaining three (3) signify as agree. The highest mean for the challenges of the grade 11 STEM students in MSU – Sulu Senior High School in facing Technology – Mediated Instruction is 3.16 and it signifies as agree. The second highest mean is 2.72 which signify as agree; while the lowest mean is 2.01 which signifies as disagree.

However, the overall mean of the result for all statements is 2.47% which falls on the scale disagree. It means that majority of the respondents disagreed to the statements given about the challenges in Technology - Mediated Instruction: its effect to academic performance among grade 11 STEM students in Mindanao State University – Sulu.

Table 4.2. Level of Academic Performance of Grade 11 STEM students in MSU-Sulu during Technology Mediated – Instruction.

Academic Performance	Mean	Verbal Description
Grade 11 STEM students	88.38%	Very Satisfactory

Legend: Outstanding = 90-100; Very Satisfactory = 85-89; Satisfactory = 80-84; fairly Satisfactory = 75-79; Did not meet the expectation = 74 below.

Table 4.2, shows the level of academic performance of the grade 11 STEM students. As shown in the table, the overall general percentage average grade of the respondents is **88.38%** with a verbal description of **very satisfactory**. This means that the level of academic performance of the students during Technology – Mediated Instruction is very satisfactory.

According to Garrison and Kanuka (2004), they examined the transformative potential of Technology - Mediated Instruction and reported an increase in course completion rates, improved retention and increased student satisfaction.

Table 4.3. Significant relationship between the Challenges in Technology Mediated – Instruction and Academic Performance among grade 11 STEM students.

	χ^2	df	P – Value	Phi (ϕ)	Decision Rule	Remarks
Challenges Academic Performance	1604.794a	1602	.476	3.837	Accept H_0	Not Significant

P-Value of 0.05 and below are Significant and above 0.05 are not significant.

Table 4.3, Chi – Square Test was performed to examine the effects of the challenges of Technology – Mediated Instruction towards the academic performance of students. Analysis of data revealed that χ^2 (1, N=109) = 1604.794a, $p = .476$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted; there is no effect on the challenges in Technology – mediated Instruction towards the academic performance of the students. This means that the grades of the respondents are not affected by the challenges in Technology – Mediated Instruction.

According to Kenney and Newcombe (2011), as they did their comparison to establish effectiveness in view of grades, they found that students who participate in Technology - Mediated Instruction had higher average score than those in a non-Technology - Mediated Instruction environment.

Conclusions

The research paper entitled Challenges in Technology - Mediated Instruction: Its Effect to Academic Performance among Grade 11 STEM Students in Mindanao State University-Sulu has finally achieved its research questions and had made the researchers provenly concluded that taking part in the Technology - Mediated Instruction as a learning concept, the academic performance of the grade 11 STEM students is not being affected by its challenges. In general, it can be said that the pupils still have high GPA even when employing this type of learning idea. To conclude, with Technology - Mediated Instruction, students are not experiencing a hard time and also does not struggle with the new learning platform. Furthermore, the Technology - Mediated Instruction does not only affect the students' learning concept, but also causes a difference in teachers' way of teaching. However, the results demonstrated that even with the challenges brought by the new learning platform, they still managed to maintain their life balance, time management, health, and successfully pushed through the challenges with positive results.

Recommendations

After successfully gathering the data, analyze and interpret, the researchers have summarized the findings, concluded and made up recommendations. The following recommendations were established from the previous chapter of the study.

1. Students should be guided by parents and teachers in order to avoid poor task management.
2. Students must be motivated and inspired by the teachers and parents to avoid lack of interest towards the subjects.
3. Parents should be mindful and minimize the amount of household chores in order to avoid constant distraction.
4. Teachers and parents should monitor the students for them to avoid constant distraction from social media.
5. School Administrators should provide good internet connection to help student with their activities.
6. Students should go to the library more often if they don't have any gadgets.
7. Students should learn how to effectively manage their time.
8. Students should not be shy to consult their teachers if they don't understand the topic.
9. Students should always have a desire for more knowledge.
10. Teachers should try to give more exciting activities for the students to give them more motivation.

Research Agenda

The following research topics in relation with findings and conclusions of this study is highly recommended by the researchers. To further understand on how Technology – Mediated Instruction caused challenges and effects on the academic performance of the students, the recommended research topics are as follows.

1. Disadvantage of Technology – Mediated Instruction: It's effect to the Academic Performance
2. Students' Ineffective Time Management: Its effect to Academic Performance
3. Technology – Mediated Instruction: Teachers' response to challenges and struggles.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby declare that an informed consent was obtained from the respondents of the study. In addition, the researchers assure that the information gathered from respondents are kept confidential. Plagiarism was strictly observed throughout the research process, and that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research purposes.

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